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**Report on Improving Parallel I/O, and Enabling
In-Situ and Compression Algorithms in
Plasma-PEPSC Codes**

WP4: Extreme Data Analytics for Plasma Simulations

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Executive Summary

This report provides updates on the implementation of parallel I/O and its performance for selected Plasma-PEPSC codes. It dives deeply into several asynchronous and hybrid in-situ techniques for real-time data analysis and discusses lossless and lossy compression and reduced precision arithmetics for data storage, communication, and computation. These innovations aim to optimize data workflows, support large-scale simulations, and mitigate storage bottlenecks inherent to modern HPC systems. The report demonstrates substantial improvements in scalability, resilience, and computational throughput, essential for advancing plasma physics research in an exascale computing era.

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1 Introduction

This text reports on recent work in improving Parallel I/O, enabling in-situ data analytics workflows and data compression.

High-Performance Computing (HPC) applications leveraging the continuously increasing peak performance of HPC systems can benefit data-intensive research. Plasma Physics simulations based on computationally expensive numerical methods profit immensely from this, producing more data than ever [33].

However, the storage capacity of HPC systems is restricted and this may limit the frequency of storing results for further analysis, which could limit scientific discovery.

Another negative factor is that the input/output (IO) subsystem is also developing relatively slowly compared to the computational power and, thus, increasingly becoming a major bottleneck that limits an application's performance.

Conventionally, the results generated by an application are stored via the IO subsystem to the storage on HPC systems. This data is then read back by data analysis applications, again stressing the IO subsystems. Thus, enabling simulation codes to use the maximum bandwidth of parallel file systems is a first step in accelerating data-driven workflows.

While compression can reduce the amount of data stored and potentially increase throughput, the time spent for compressing and decompressing data has to be taken into account as detailed in [23]. Compression can be used both in I/O and in-situ.

In-situ techniques can help alleviate these problems by processing data directly at their place or on dedicated resources without writing and reading through the IO subsystem to and from the storage.

Traditional in-situ techniques with static resource management can be categorized into three types depending on how the task interrupts the original application: in the *synchronous* approach (Fig. 1(a)), the in-situ task pauses the application until it has finished; in the *asynchronous* approach (Fig. 1(b)), extra resources execute the in-situ task, while the application continues its execution after having sent the data to these resources; in the *hybrid approach* (Fig. 1(c)), one part of the in-situ task pauses the original application, while separate resources execute the rest; it is a combination of the synchronous and asynchronous approach.

In-situ workflows can avoid or reduce the IO throughput and storage, and proper choice among the three in-situ techniques can minimize the overhead brought by the in-situ techniques. Asynchronous and hybrid in-situ techniques are typically preferred for poorly scaling in-situ task [10, 24, 25]. However, they require separate resources. In many real-world scenarios, the in-situ processing will only start after a certain period. Therefore, these resources may stay idle for a significant amount of time. Strongly coupled in-situ techniques avoid data movement entirely, using in-place transformation of data [30, 32].

With dynamic resource management, one can allocate and release additional computing resources for in-situ tasks, avoiding leaving them idle, as shown in Fig. 1(d) and (e) compared to static resource allocations as shown in Fig. 1(b) and (c). In this document, we focus on the asynchronous and/or hybrid in-situ approaches, and thus refer to them when using the term *in-situ*, unless we explicitly specify the synchronous in-situ approach.

Figure 1: **Illustration of synchronous, asynchronous, and hybrid in-situ techniques with static resource management and asynchronous and hybrid in-situ techniques with dynamic resource management.** Asynchronous or hybrid in-situ technique with dynamic resource management has less idle time than asynchronous or hybrid in-situ technique with static resource management. Strongly coupled in-situ techniques are not depicted, as they do not require data movement at all.

The introduction of MPI Sessions [18] in the MPI Standard 4.0 [31] provides a new degree of flexibility and modularity in MPI, which could make MPI more suitable for elastic in-situ workloads [9]. A recent approach [12, 21, 20] introduced dynamic MPI Process interface extensions for MPI Sessions and an implementation based on Open MPI [13].

Complex asynchronous in-situ workflows, including reduction, compression and code coupling, are available via the openPMD library that accelerates I/O and provides in-memory coupling, as detailed in the following section.

2 Parallel I/O

Increasing parallel I/O performance is crucial for

- Writing checkpoints to increase resilience,
- Writing high quality simulation data for later analysis
- Reading simulation data from disk for further analysis or visualization.

In the following sections we discuss recent I/O improvements to some Plasma-PEPSC codes.

2.1 New features of the openPMD-API

The openPMD-api, a library utilized within the Plasma-PEPSC initiative by the simulation codes PIconGPU and BIT1, has recently been updated to version 0.16.0 [22]. This release introduces enhanced support for parallel I/O operations, further extending its compatibility with the ADIOS2 and HDF5 I/O frameworks. For HDF5, this includes support for the subfilng virtual file driver, a technique necessary for avoiding I/O bottlenecks in output procedures beyond a medium scale. More precise control over independent writing has been added in order to allow applications to use the most efficient I/O methods matching the parallel application logic.

For ADIOS2, support for asynchronous background-writing has been added. The metadata aggregation logic has been greatly improved for extreme-scale applications with collective metadata logic (the usual case due to similar constraints imposed by HDF5). Support for the “joined array” dataset geometry has been added, reducing the number of collective operations needed for data preparation, and thus also reducing the API complexity for data preparation in simulation codes. Data files created with the openPMD-api via ADIOS2 can now optionally use an encoding that allows rapid inspection of data while it is being written, useful for inspecting partial data after a crash in parallel setups, enabling better diagnostics of errors. Support for ADIOS2 steps as an alternative to creating a new output file per simulation step has been improved, offering an I/O strategy with a far lower filesystem load for use cases with high-frequency output. An additional dataset geometry is available in a development version for using the metadata aggregation system in small-sized datasets, crucial for communication e.g. particle metadata in scalable streaming-I/O setups without requiring a fully connected communication mesh.

For simplified debugging of parallel I/O, parallel JSON-based structure output has been added as an alternative to full output via HDF5/ADIOS2.

2.2 BIT1 I/O Improvements

Introducing parallel I/O in Particle-in-Cell (PIC) Monte Carlo (MC) simulations is crucial, as it enables the efficient handling of data streams from multiple computational processes simultaneously. This parallel approach enhances throughput, reduces the time required for data storage and retrieval, and accelerates the pace of scientific discovery, thereby broadening the scope of simulations. Despite significant advances in computing capabilities, a persistent challenge remains in mitigating the performance bottleneck posed by I/O systems, which can hinder scientific progress and limit the potential of PIC MC simulations.

BIT1, a 1D3V electrostatic PIC MC code, simulates plasma, impurity, and neutral transport in magnetic flux tubes of the plasma edge [39, 40, 41]. Despite its reduced dimensionality, BIT1 captures a broad range of kinetic processes, enabling novel plasma studies [38]. BIT1’s input is a compact file (1–3 kB), while the output workflows are defined by five critical parameters in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters for system diagnostics and simulation control.

Parameter	Description
datfile	Saves the system’s diagnostic snapshot at a specific time step.
dmpstep	Defines when the system’s current state, including particle data, is saved.
mvflag	Activates time-dependent diagnostics for plasma profiles and particle distributions. If > 0 , it sets the number of steps over which diagnostics are averaged.
mvStep	Sets the interval between time-dependent diagnostics. Controls how often the data is collected.
last_step	Marks the final time step, saving the state to disk and ending the simulation. This ensures the completion of the simulation.

As described in [45, 43], D4.1, and identified during development, BIT1’s original serial output supports up to 20,000 MPI processes effectively but struggles with larger-scale simulations, where output becomes slow and prone to corruption. Addressing these limitations requires the implementation of parallel I/O methods to ensure scalability and data integrity for extensive HPC workloads.

Figure 2: BIT1 Original File I/O Write Throughput, on Discoverer, Dardel and Vega CPU LFS, up to 200 Nodes, measured in GiB/s. [44]

In [44], the openPMD-api parallel I/O library was integrated into BIT1 using the ADIOS2 backend BP4. The I/O performance of BIT1 was evaluated on the following three systems:

- **Discoverer:** A petascale EuroHPC supercomputer featuring:
 - 1128 compute nodes,

- AMD EPYC processors,
 - A 2.1 PB Lustre File System.
- **Dardel:** An HPE Cray EX supercomputer characterized by:
 - 1270 compute nodes,
 - AMD EPYC processors,
 - A 12 PB Lustre File System.
 - **Vega:** A petascale EuroHPC supercomputer equipped with:
 - 960 compute nodes,
 - AMD EPYC processors,
 - A 23 PB Ceph File System.

The diversity of network and storage configurations across these systems enabled a comprehensive assessment of BIT1’s I/O performance.

Fig. 2 displays the performance of traditional file I/O in BIT1 on Discoverer, Dardel, and Vega CPU LFS. The Discoverer CPU exhibited poor scalability, with write throughput declining by 23% from 0.26 GiB/s (1 node) to 0.20 GiB/s (200 nodes). In contrast, the Dardel CPU demonstrated better parallelism, with throughput increasing from 0.09 GiB/s to 0.41 GiB/s. The Vega CPU showed inconsistent performance, lacking clear scaling behavior. As Dardel provided the highest throughput at scale, further investigations focused on its CPU LFS, which was also applicable to Discoverer, Vega and other HPC systems.

Figure 3: BIT1 Original File I/O and openPMD + BP4 Write Throughput on Dardel up to 200 Nodes, measured in GiB/s. [44]

In Fig. 3, BIT1’s original serial I/O displays increased write throughput for small runs, peaking before decreasing due to metadata write overhead for larger runs [45]. In contrast, BIT1 with openPMD BP4 backend achieves more stable throughput by leveraging parallel I/O to efficiently distribute workloads and mitigate metadata overhead.

2.3 BIT1 I/O Costs Per Process

Reducing I/O runtime is critical to improve the efficiency, scalability, and cost-effectiveness of computational BIT1 simulations. As highlighted in [45, 43] and D4.1, peak I/O write throughput depends on problem size and degrades beyond the peak due to increasing metadata costs in large runs. To investigate further, the time spent in I/O functions on 200 nodes was analyzed, comparing BIT1’s original I/O method with openPMD using the ADIOS2 BP4 backend [44]. Fig. 4 presents normalized results for average I/O reads, writes, and metadata costs per process.

Figure 4: BIT1 Average I/O Cost Per Process on Dardel for Reads, Metadata and Writes on 200 nodes, normalized. [44]

The integration of openPMD with BP4 demonstrated significant improvements. Metadata overhead was reduced by 99.92%, with the average metadata time per process dropping from 17.868 seconds (BIT1 Original I/O) to 0.014 seconds. Similarly, write operations improved, with average write time per process decreasing from 1.043 seconds (BIT1 Original I/O) to 0.009 seconds, representing a 99.14% reduction. This satisfies the KPI for reducing runtime overhead of I/O activities by 20%. This KPI along with the KPI for total analytics overhead are demonstrated in [44].

3 In-situ data analysis

In-situ data analysis addresses several challenges in high-performance simulations, including reducing the need for extensive data transfers and overcoming limited I/O bandwidth, especially on exascale systems. Processing data directly within the simulation environment mitigates the inefficiency of writing large-scale outputs to storage and improves performance in heterogeneous pipelines with differing scaling properties.

Figure 5: Performing a real-time checkpoint analysis of the BIT1 openPMD BP4 simulation on the Dardel CPU LFS, using 12,800 MPI processes up to 200K time steps, revealing key plasma profiles, particle load per MPI rank, and the time evolution of total particles for each species. [42]

3.1 Improvements of in-situ data analysis in BIT1

In-situ analysis enables real-time data assessment within the simulation environment, eliminating the need for extensive data transfers. BIT1 tracks total particle numbers over time with minimal diagnostics and can log additional parameters like particle and power fluxes, depending on the input. It also supports periodic system state saving for checkpointing and restoration.

Fig. 5, as well as the findings reported in [42], show a real-time checkpoint analysis of BIT1 File I/O stored in the output directory, `data_file.bp4`, using a custom Python script with the openPMD API and ADIOS2 BP4 backend for 12,800 MPI processes. Visualizations include electric potential, plasma species densities, and temperatures, providing insights into plasma sheath presence and electric field utilization. MPI workload distribution is also visualized to ensure balanced computation.

The simulation’s steady-state is assessed by tracking the total particle count for each species, revealing dynamics such as the increase in electron and ion numbers and the decrease in neutral particles due to ionization. In-situ analysis offers immediate insights, allowing efficient simulation adjustments without any system interruption.

3.2 Improvements of in-situ data analysis in GENE / GENE-X

3.2.1 Dynamic In-situ Techniques

For the sake of simplicity, we first assume that we have infinite resources, i.e., the in-situ task can get the required resources immediately. Fig. 6 illustrates the workflow of the

Figure 6: **The workflow of the basic dynamic in-situ technique.** The figure depicts when the original application processes (the left half) request new resources for the in-situ task (the right half) and how the original application (the left half) and the in-situ task (the right half) interact in the basic dynamic in-situ technique.

basic dynamic in-situ approach. When the original application reaches the first step to execute the in-situ task, it requests additional computing resources for the in-situ task. In complex simulations, this phase could take a very long time. For instance, in the plasma simulation GENE-X [33], 1.0 ms of real-time took 2.5 million CPU hours (MCPUh) on 256 Intel Skylake nodes [1]. One can see that turbulence starts at 0.2 ms, hence, it would take about two days for 256 Intel Skylake nodes to reach the turbulent state [34]. Thus, it is beneficial to ask for additional resources only when we reach the turbulent state. Once the new resources have been obtained, the data required for the in-situ task are sent to them, the in-situ task is executed and then simulation proceeds with further iterations.

This basic dynamic in-situ technique requires the user to decide the amount of resources allocated to the in-situ task, which typically requires systematic tests to obtain a good resource estimate and/or the use of complex performance models. Our advanced in-situ dynamic technique (Fig. 7) avoids this. Instead of the user specifying the additional resources, the program automatically asks for a small group of resources and uses them for the first step of the in-situ task. This is typically one node in our implementation, as the prototype of the MPI Sessions extensions we use for the process dynamicity

Figure 7: **The workflow of the advanced dynamic in-situ technique.**The figure depicts when the original application processes (the left half) request new resources for the in-situ task (the right half) and how the original application (the left half) and the in-situ task (the right half) interact in the advanced dynamic in-situ technique.

currently only allows new MPI processes to be launched on new nodes. We therefore launch sufficient MPI processes to use the whole new node. When the second step of the in-situ task needs to be executed, the application checks if the in-situ task has finished and its resources can be used again. If this is not the case, another group of resources is allocated and used for the second in-situ step. This is repeated every time an in-situ task should be started; thus, the set of resources is growing dynamically, if necessary.

3.2.2 Implementation using MPI Sessions and DPP

To achieve the required process dynamicity we used the Dynamic Processes with Process Sets (DPP) approach [20]. DPP is a set of generic design principles to enable dynamic resource management of high-performance parallel programming models such as MPI. It uses a co-design approach to provide the flexibility for application developers to express specific, dynamic resource requirements of applications while allowing the resource man-

Figure 8: Illustration of using MPI Sessions and the DPP approach to enable dynamic resources for the basic and advanced dynamic in-situ approaches. The figure depicts how the original application processes (left column) and the processes of the in-situ task (right column) use process sets and set operations (middle column) for dynamic process management and communicator creation throughout the different phases of the dynamic in-situ workflows.

agement software to optimize the resource utilization of the HPC system. DPP abstracts access to resources via *process sets* (*PSets*), and resource (re-)assignments as *process set operations*, leading to a *graph-based* description of the applications' resource assignments.

We used a prototype implementation [19] of the DPP approach based on OpenMPI, which provides an extended MPI Sessions interface for dynamic resources. The prototype adds two basic functionalities to the MPI Sessions routines defined in the MPI Standard 4.0. First, routines to interact with the resource manager by sending and querying *process set operations* which express resource reconfigurations. Second, routines to access a *global dictionary* where key-value pairs can be associated with a particular process set (PSet) Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) for sharing application-specific information across PSets. For brevity, we refer the reader to [20] for a more detailed description of the interface extensions.

Fig. 8 illustrates the usage of this extended MPI Sessions interface during the different phases of the program flow of the dynamic in-situ approaches. The left column represents the processes of the original application, the right column represents the processes of the

in-situ task(s), and the middle column shows the associated MPI process sets.

Original Application Initialization: The original application processes are started with the `mpirun` command (2 processes in this example). After initializing an MPI Session, the processes create a common MPI communicator for the original application using the `mpi://WORLD` URI. Note that `mpi://WORLD` is a local alias for the URI `PSet://1` containing the original application processes $\{p1, p2\}$. This is the MPI Session equivalent of using `MPI_COMM_WORLD` in the MPI World model. Subsequently, the original application uses this created communicator for the communication during the *Original Application Steps*.

Resources Request: If additional resources are required, the resource manager is contacted via the extended MPI Sessions interface. To this end, an MPI PSet operation of type *GROW* is specified, where the URI `PSet://1` is the input to the operation (black arrows in Fig. 8). The resource manager considers the specified process set operation in its scheduling algorithm and will eventually apply the advocated PSet operation by creating the two output PSets with URIs `PSet://2` and `PSet://3`. These URIs are returned to the original application processes.

`PSet://2` refers to the newly created processes $\{p3, p4\}$ (possibly on added resources) while `PSet://3` refers to the union of `PSet://1` and `PSet://2`. The newly created processes initialize an MPI Session and create a communicator for the in-situ task from the `mpi://WORLD` URI. Note, that here `mpi://WORLD` is a local alias for `PSet://2` containing processes $\{p3, p4\}$. This is similar to disjoint `MPI_COMM_WORLD` communicators with `MPI_Comm_spawn`. Processes can determine if they were launched dynamically via the MPI info object associated with `mpi://WORLD`.

To establish communication with the original processes a common communicator has to be created from `PSet://3`. To this end, the original processes publish the URI `PSet://3` in the global dictionary associated with `PSet://2`, where the dynamically added processes can look up this information and participate in the communicator construction (purple arrows in Fig. 8). This common communicator can then be used for the *Data Transfer* from the original application to the in-situ task, e.g. after each application step.

Application Finalization: To terminate application processes, these processes must disconnect from all communicators they are part of before finalizing the MPI Session. While `MPI_Comm_disconnect` is a collective and potentially synchronizing call on the processes within the communicator, `MPI_Session_finalize` is a local function.

Therefore, the original application processes and the in-situ task processes can terminate independently. In this case, an MPI PSet operation of type *SUB* could be specified for a given PSet URI to release the resources associated with this PSet. However, in our implementation, we did not release resources prematurely, as the original application and in-situ tasks terminate almost simultaneously.

3.2.3 Evaluation of Dynamic In-situ Techniques

All the experiments are performed on the Raven supercomputer at the Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF) [2]. One CPU node contains two Intel Xeon IceLake-SP 8360Y processors, each with 36 cores and 256 GB RAM. We repeated the same experiments three times and only reported the average here because of negligible

Figure 9: **Resource usage of GENE-X with in-situ image generation.** The resource utilization for communication and in-situ tasks is barely visible and the dynamic asynchronous approaches (right two bars) have fewer idle resources

differences among different runs. Dynamic Resource Management on HPC systems necessitates new optimization algorithms for global (dynamic) scheduling which is an active research area beyond the scope of our work. Since current production-level resource managers such as Slurm do not yet support dynamic scheduling we reserved enough resources for the original application and the in-situ task. Then, the application is started with less than the reserved resources, requesting in-situ resources dynamically over its runtime. We compute the resource usage c using

$$c = \sum_i^m n_i \times t_i \quad (1)$$

with n_i the occupied computing nodes, their respective occupancy times t_i and m is the number of process groups. For our tests, we assume that resources are immediately available. While this might not always be the case on HPC systems with dynamic scheduling policies, our evaluation provides a baseline to understand the performance behavior of dynamic in-situ techniques.

We executed a total of 200 simulation steps. From the 100th time step on, we performed one in-situ image generation every simulation step. We used four nodes for the

static synchronous and asynchronous in-situ approaches. We used two MPI processes on each node with 36 OpenMP threads per MPI process for the static synchronous approach. For the static asynchronous in-situ approach, we specified a CPU ID binding mask for each MPI process to correctly pin the threads to the process. We measured the shortest total execution time in our tests with the following configuration: two cores on each node are assigned to the two in-situ MPI processes, while the rest are to the simulation (two MPI processes and 35 cores per MPI process). Since image generation is not a computationally heavy task, we started the simulation with four nodes and added one additional node for the in-situ task in the basic dynamic approach. For the advanced dynamic approach, we started the simulation with four nodes, and the simulation automatically added one additional node for the in-situ task.

As shown in Fig. 9, although the basic dynamic asynchronous approach avoids leaving the MPI process waiting for 100 simulation steps, it takes only a slightly shorter time than the static asynchronous approach, because the image generation is computationally cheaper than the simulation. The static asynchronous approach only uses two cores per node for image generation and avoids idle cores during image generation; the static synchronous approach requires no resources waiting for data, but it leaves the 35 cores per MPI processes idle when the image generation is executed; the default configuration of dynamic MPI processes added by MPI Sessions stays the same as the simulation, which leads to 35 cores per MPI process idle like the static synchronous approach. In this test case, the basic and advanced dynamic approaches use the same amount of resources. The total resource usage of the basic approach is slightly better due to a small difference in the communication time.

3.3 Improvements of in-situ data analysis in Vlasiator

Vlasiator’s I/O subsystem is structured around the concept of a “data reducer”, with the idea of large-scale simulations as numerical experiments in mind. The most generic data reducers perform nothing but straightforward transformations of simulation data, such as writing electromagnetic field quantities or reduced velocity space moments into output files. With the increasing scale of global magnetospheric runs, it has become infeasible to write more than a handful of these quantities at full simulation cadence, and a more focussed in-situ analysis approach has been taken into action since the start of the Plasma-PEPSC project.

Two examples of in-situ data analysis in Vlasiator that directly output science data are:

- In [17], an in-situ data reducer running at high cadence during the simulation was used to obtain ionospheric ion precipitation spectra. By continuously classifying each phase space cell of the 6-dimensional magnetosphere simulation volume, it is possible to determine which parts of the near-Earth plasma population would follow the magnetic field lines into the ionosphere, where they can excite aurora and other ionospheric phenomena.

The in-situ analysis process reduced the 6D simulation volume to a set of effectively 2D precipitation spectra, obviating the need to write significant amounts of phase space for post-processing.

- In [36], massively parallel in-situ fieldline tracing with starting points in every simulation cell is employed to find the magnetic connectivity and topological structures in the magnetospheric magnetic fields. In this particular publication, the mechanism was used to find flux ropes – wound structures of magnetic field lines. The same mechanism can also be employed to determine which parts of the simulation is magnetically connected to Earth, meaning that plasma phenomena in those regions can directly impinge onto Earth’s atmosphere.

Performing this step in-situ, using full electromagnetic field data and high-order derivative information, is both more precise and faster than a postprocessing approach.

3.4 Improvements of in-situ data analysis in PIConGPU

The year 2024 has seen an exploration into practical solutions for performing in-situ application coupling for analysis on the raw data produced by PIConGPU at the full scale of Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility (OLCF) Frontier. In-situ hereby refers to a data strategy where data is exchanged from one application’s memory to another application’s memory, possibly located on another compute unit, without using permanent storage for the task. This strategy is chosen for a multitude of reasons:

1. Integrating all parts of a scientific data processing pipeline into a single application is often *not possible* due to vastly different software environments. The example at hand is a data processing pipeline consisting of the accelerated C++ simulation code PIConGPU and a PyTorch-based machine learning model for inferring the relation between the phase space characteristics and the particle trajectories causing the phase space.
2. Integrating all parts of a scientific data processing pipeline into a single application is often *not desirable* due to vastly different scaling properties of heterogeneous stages in a data processing pipeline. Here, PIConGPU scales up to full system size while the used PyTorch code scales up to only a medium portion of the system before being overwhelmed by collective communication operations.
3. Using the parallel filesystem is generally no longer possible on recent Exascale compute systems due to limited I/O bandwidth and capacity in relation to the amounts of raw data produced by accelerated simulation codes.
4. An alternative should allow flexible communication patterns without locking scientists into a tightly specified application setup, as techniques like shared memory or node-local SSDs for data exchange inevitably would. Communication must hence be in-transit, making use of HPC network interconnects.

PIConGPU was tested against a synthetic data consumer to test scalability of Streaming I/O via the OLCF Frontier’s Slingshot network at medium to full scale, using different implementations to access the Slingshot network for remote direct memory access (RDMA). The measured performance results are seen in Fig. 10.

The PIConGPU Kelvin–Helmholtz instability (KHI) simulation is used as a reference, producing 5.86 GB of particle data per compute node and time step. At each scaling run

Figure 10: **Parallel total throughput for streaming at full scale on Frontier using a synthetic benchmark built on PIconGPU KHI.** An obvious outlier result was removed for the libfabric backend at 8192 nodes. (a) Using the libfabric data plane and the CXI provider to access the Slingshot network at a lower level. (b) Using the MPI data plane based on `MPI_Open_port()`. The perceived parallel throughput reaches around 20TB/s for libfabric, and from 20 - 30 TB/s for MPI.

(weak scaling), five time steps are sent from PIconGPU to the no-op consumer, which then measures the time needed for loading the data. The perceived parallel throughput is computed based on this measured time and the global data size, i.e. the previously mentioned 5.86 GB per node multiplied with the number of nodes. While including communication overhead, this perceived parallel throughput has been shown in [10] to be a close approximation for the real throughput in this kind of setup.

The benchmarks depicted in Fig. 10 demonstrate the feasibility of this I/O strategy for full-scale workflows. Depicted are boxplots of all single measurements. Most notably, we observe a maximum perceived parallel throughput of 20 - 30 TB/s which compares outstandingly against the 10 TB/s bandwidth of the parallel Orion filesystem, a scaling limit which we circumvent and exceed by not using the filesystem for intermediate data. Furthermore, these results can also compare well against the 35 TB/s aggregate write bandwidth of the SSDs installed locally in the compute nodes [3].

For the libfabric-based benchmarks, we initially used an implementation that enqueued all read operations to the network at once and waited for replies (labeled 4096* in Fig. 10). While these results signify the best achieved per-node throughput of 3.5 - 4.7 GB/s at 4096 compute nodes (*a total of 14.1 - 18.8 TB/s*), it turned out that this strategy did not scale to the full system, so we employed an alternative that enqueued operations in batches of 10 operations. While this turned out to scale to the full system, it came at a notable cost in performance, visible in a per-node throughput of 1.9 - 2.6 GB/s at 9126 compute nodes (*a total of 16.5 - 23.0 TB/s*). Conversely, the MPI data plane yields a per-node throughput from 2.6 - 3.7 GB/s at 4096 compute nodes (*a total of 10.5 - 14.9 TB/s*) to 2.4 - 3.3 GB/s at 9126 nodes (*a total of 21.4 - 29.5 TB/s*), **the best achieved system-wide parallel throughput** from this experiment.

We conclude that the MPI data plane brings default good performance, while the libfabric data plane’s lower-level control can bring performance improvements but at the cost of necessary fine-tuning beyond this study’s scope. Since only a single instance of

the reader code was running per node, its throughput (1.9 - 4.7 GB/s, across all cases) compares against the max possible throughput of a single HPE Slingshot NIC at 25 GB/s. This implies that further speedup can be achieved by parallelizing the reader in the actual PIconGPU+MLapp pipeline. The benchmarks suggest that the MPI data plane be used, which can be explained by leveraging system-specific performance tuning in the MPI implementation. All regular measurements range between 1.2 s - 3.2 s.

Future investigations will include data aggregation patterns for streaming I/O in order to support the different sizes at which both ends of the data processing pipeline scale, as well as increased per-node parallelism for making better use of the network access reachable from processes executing on a compute node.

4 Compression Methods

The four flagship codes enable simulations that require a large amount of data to be handled during and after simulations. In this section, we describe how lossless and lossy compression can be used to speed up simulations, increase throughput and reduce storage usage after simulations.

During simulations, a limiting factor for performance is communication and data movement. Fast intra-node memory connectivity and network-based inter-node communication is crucial for the scalability of the code. The compression of data that is communicated between parallel instances of a code can improve communication and the time to solution. A complete analysis must include the time for compression and decompression to estimate overall speed up due to compression. One of the main questions for such methods is to determine when communication with compression and decompression is faster than communication with non-compressed data. Multiple compression libraries have been evaluated and ZFP was chosen for the deeper evaluation, which is presented in section 4.1.

During and after a successful simulation, a large amount of storage is required to store the particle and field information. This is a growing problem in the field as larger simulations with better resolution and more correct representation of physical phenomena generate more data. Storage is both costly and energy-intensive, presenting scientists with a challenging dilemma: either retain large volumes of data at significant expense or risk deleting data that is essential for preservation and accessibility within the scientific process. To enable the use of compression libraries in I/O the effort to integrate it in `openPMD-api` is described in section 4.2.

These large simulations also require resilience measures, as interruptions that lead to canceled simulations are expensive (scientist’s time as well as core hours). Therefore, in I/O tasks such as check-pointing and long-term storage lossy compression is advantageous. This task has explored Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) as a Machine Learning approach for the compression of particle data described in section 4.3 mainly intended to be used in check-pointing but can also be useful for post-processing and analysis of large simulations.

Compression can be used to lower the memory consumption of a simulation, improving memory-bound algorithms. One way of compressing data is to represent it with a lower accuracy floating-point representation. This work focuses on experimental validation of analytic error estimates for spatial discretization and its required floating-point precision in finite difference calculations. This has been performed with a library designed to do floating-point calculations with arbitrary precision described in section 4.4. The study has concluded that some simulations waste memory and compute by over-resolving low-resolution problems.

4.1 Leveraging Compression Libraries for Communication

As mentioned on the previous deliverable: *D4.1 Initial Report on Improving Parallel I/O, Enabling In-situ and Compression*, Max Planck Gesellschaft (MPG), through Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF) and Max-Planck Institut für Plasma-physik (MPG IPP), is involved in a German-funded project titled *Data Reduction for Exascale Application in Fusion Research* (DaREXA-F). Within this project, MPCDF

Figure 11: **Measuring ZFP compression/decompression overhead with respect to uncompressed communications.** Given a simple send-receive communication scheme within pairs of ranks holding their data in GPU device buffers, compressed communication is viable for data exchanges larger than 10^7 bytes.

has been exploring lossy compression methods with a focus on inter-node communication as part of distributed computations. In particular, after evaluating lossy compression libraries like ZFP [29, 7], MGARD [4, 27, 16] and SZ [6, 37, 26, 28] for performance and data compressibility, ZFP was chosen as the most performant and easy to adopt given GENE’s complex numerical data, comprising both real and imaginary components.

One of the main challenges in using in-simulation data compression for communication is ensuring the compression and decompression processes are fast enough to minimize overhead, ideally making it negligible. Fig. 11 displays an evaluation performed with the ZFP compressor where GPU-based data is compressed before it is communicated and decompressed on the receiving end. Given different values of Compression Factor ($CF = \frac{\text{Uncompressed Size}}{\text{Compressed Size}}$), we can see that costs of compression overhead make it viable only to use compression for messages larger than approximately 10 to 12 MB. However, as shown in Table 2, for a target scenario of an ITER-like problem size and given a reasonable parallelization in GENE (assuming roughly 8640 GPUs are used), the biggest message exchanges would be in the order of 7.5 MB.

We have developed a scheme that enables us to hide some of the compression and decompression costs by overlapping these operations with the communication of compressed data to reduce the message size threshold at which compressed communications provide performance returns. To do this, a modified version of the ZFP library that supports encoding and decoding kernels to be executed on user-defined GPU streams is used in hand with the NVIDIA Collective Communications Library (NCCL), which provides point-to-point operations for data exchange across devices streams. This overlapped scheme has been introduced into GENE’s v-direction boundary exchange operation in which the

Table 2: **Expected dimensions of a message size in the exchange_v_6d operation in global-mode GENE for an ITER-like scenario of burning-plasma.** GENE buffers in this exchange operation are double precision complex numbers.

Dimensions	Size (Minimal ITER-like sizes)	MPI Ranks	sbuf_shape	Message Size
nx0	1024	4	256	~7.5 MB
nky0	96	3	32	
nz0	24	12	6	
nv0	32	4	2	
nw0	25	5	5	
n_spec	3	3	1	

data is then compressed and decompressed during each neighbor exchange. We have evaluated this new communication scheme using a Cyclone-Base case in GENE and ran experiments on the GPU partition of the Raven supercomputer at the MPCDF [2]. Each Raven GPU-accelerated node is comprised of 4 NVIDIA A100 GPUs, interlinked with NVLink 3 and the network connecting GPU nodes is a Mellanox Infiniband HDR200.

Table 3: **Dimensions of a message size in the exchange_v_6d operation in the Cyclone-Base Case.**

Dimensions	Size (Minimal ITER-like sizes)	MPI Ranks	sbuf_shape	Message Size
nx0	96	1	96	~7.8 MB
nky0	28	1	28	
nz0	32	4	12	
nv0	32	8	2	
nw0	8	1	8	
n_spec	1	1	1	

Table 3 shows the test case dimensions and the chosen parallelization for evaluation. The message size is close to the expected target ITER scenario and the parallelization is done in such a way that allows us to evaluate the proposed scheme under network saturation conditions, where the benefits of data compression would be useful for exascale simulations. Fig. 12 shows the mean time per timestep for the test case described in Table 3. Normal execution refers to a GENE simulation where no compression is used. This is also the baseline reference for performance. Given different levels of network usage in Raven, normal execution shows more performance variability than the compressed experiments. We use speedup ranges to quantify the effects of compression over the execution time of each time step in GENE and observe up to a 16% performance improvement when communication is done with a compression factor of 8. Furthermore, main quantities of interest resulting from compressed runs of the simulation like the spatially averaged estimated means for electrostatic heatflux and parallel velocity space moment are within [0.31% – 10.80%] of the expected value for the former and [1.51% – 2.09%] for the latter, highlighting the potential for lossy compression in GENE. In the context of this project, we will evaluate this proposed overlapped scheme also in other applications, in particular

Figure 12: **Speedups resulting from proposed overlapped compression scheme with ZFP**

Vlasiator, where previous studies [11] have shown that this is a communication-bound code where message sizes are relatively large and involve high dimensionality data.

4.2 Extending the availability of compression methods for scientific I/O

The openPMD-api, used currently among the simulation codes pertaining to Plasma-PEPSC by PIConGPU and BIT1, has so far supported compression options only via the *operator* mechanic of ADIOS2, but not yet via the *filter* mechanic of HDF5. While both these techniques are not restricted to compression methods, they offer a wide range of established compression operators, open to third-party contributors. Options include e.g. GZip, BZip2, Blosc2, SZ or ZFP. The recent release 0.16.0 of the openPMD-api [22] adds targeted configuration for HDF5 chunking, a necessary prerequisite for compression. A usable prototype for compression via HDF5 in the openPMD-api is now available as a development version¹, thus adding to the I/O flexibility of simulation codes building on this I/O solution.

4.3 Developing Statistical Methods for Plasma Simulation Data

There are multiple strategies for lossy compression based on Machine Learning and statistical methods, some described in deliverable 4.1. The main idea for using GMM in the compression of PIC data comes from the insight that in most of the simulations the velocity distribution function does not greatly deviate from a Maxwellian or a Gaussian. Therefore we can approximate the particle velocities as a Velocity Density Function (VDF) modeled as a linear combination of Gaussian distributions, which in a compressed state can be reduced to a set of mean values and variance/co-variance matrices (in higher

¹<https://github.com/openPMD/openPMD-api/pull/1644>

dimensions). The GMMs are trained on a cell-by-cell basis with an Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm, seeing the position and the velocity as two independent variables (globally dependent). The position is reconstructed by drawing from a uniform distribution. The GMM conserves charge, momentum, and energy locally. This makes the most naive algorithm completely communication-avoiding. Due to the resampling of particles from cell-wise uniform distributions Gauss' law and charge conservation is not fulfilled. A mass-matrix correction step is employed which utilizes the b-splines used in the PIC algorithm to enforce continuity in charge density discretely. This step breaks the strict conservation of momentum and energy. A key parameter of the GMM is how many components (Gaussians) should be used, an adaptive algorithm [5] has been proposed and showed promising results. Anderson acceleration of the EM algorithm [35] improves the rate of convergence of the parameter optimization. Global convergence has also been explored [46]. There is a possibility of a high rate of compression using a GMM, as a few parameters defining the set of Gaussian can represent orders of magnitude more particles.

Expectation Maximization and Gaussian Mixture Models

The goal is to estimate the parameters $\theta_k = \{\pi, \mu, \Sigma\}$ of each Gaussian with some estimation algorithm where k indicates which component and π_k is a component weight ($\sum_k^K \pi_k = 1$). There are as previously mentioned algorithms that find the optimal number of Gaussians adaptively and treat K as a parameter. The standard EM algorithm is a naive iterative method to estimate the unknown parameters:

1. **Initialization:** Initialize each of the Gaussians with a mean μ_k sampled from the particle data and unit variance.
2. **Expectation:** For each component k , perform a E-step: given the θ_k (current parameter set) calculate (2)

$$r_{ik} = \frac{\pi_k N(x_i | \mu_k, \Sigma)}{\sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k N(x_i | \mu_k, \Sigma_k)} \quad (2)$$

Where x indicates input data and the subscript i indicates the particle.

3. **Maximization:** For each component k , perform the M-step by evaluating equations in (3)

$$\pi_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m r_i}{m} \quad \mu_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ik} x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ik}}, \quad \Sigma_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ik} (x_i - \mu_c)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ik}} \quad (3)$$

4. **Convergence** repeat 2 and 3 until convergence is met usually by monitoring the likelihood function.

It is assumed that the simulations are performed mainly on the GPUs and that the CPUs are left idle for the simulation, therefore available for in-situ analysis or data compression and I/O operations. We aim to leverage `openPMD-api` to simplify the adoption of the method into one or more of the PIC-based codes.

Initial Exploration: 1D-1V two-stream electrostatic instability

The two-stream instability is an electrostatic phenomenon where two opposing particle beams interact, transferring kinetic and electrostatic energy between them, leading to the formation of a vortex in phase space. In this preliminary experiment, we utilize Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) to compress the phase space at various time intervals and recreate the particles by sampling from the generated distributions. We explore the cell-wise GMM with the VDF and a formulation where the spatial and velocity distributions are correlated in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: a) The un-compressed phase-space at $t=0.3T$ below is the state at $t=T$ after continued simulation. b) Re-sampled phases-space based on a uniform spatial distribution and Gaussian mixture with 4 components per cell. c) Re-constructed phase-space for Gaussian-Gaussian method. In this case, the positions (mean) of the Gaussians are denoted with black and orange points.

Initial experiments and literature review show promising results for GMMs as a method for enabling the KPIs for the compression task (T4.3) as well as the resilience work (T3.3). Future work will focus on method development aimed at improving the description of the spatial distribution to minimize the need for global correction steps.

4.4 Reduced Precision Methods

PIConGPU provides full support of mixed precision arithmetic over the whole code, using single precision whenever feasible. Further reduced precision methods are provided by the LLAMA library (see D5.2). Extensive tests have shown that in very few cases double precision is needed. On GPUs, further reduction in precision is of interest when using built-in types, while user-defined types for arbitrary precision have not proven efficient. However, 8 bit precision or less has been found detrimental for accuracy of physics results.

Within the German-funded project DaREXA-F already mentioned in Section 4.1 above, MPG IPP is exploring the usability of reduced size floating point types and the

applicability of mixed precision techniques in GENE. These efforts are presented in the following paragraphs. Advancements in this context potentially also leverage the I/O in GENE code (GENE): e.g., if in certain simulation scenarios a lower precision (and hence less memory demanding) representation of the distribution function turns out to be tenable to preserve the simulation dynamics, this would proportionally impact the I/O memory requirements for checkpointing in GENE.

Enabling reduced and mixed precision GENE simulations

The extension of the GTENSOR library [14, 15] to 16-bit floating point (FP) types reported in the D4.1 deliverable was the first step towards running GENE in low precision (16-bit). Apart from infrastructure work within GENE itself, most notably the REG_STORAGE library enabling heterogeneous hardware memory allocations in GENE was extended to allow for 16-bit type memory allocations. Combining these efforts, first GENE runs were carried out using half precision types on the GPU. In the results shown in Fig. 14 the velocity space moment calculation was performed with lower precision (FP32, FP16, BF16) while all other computations were done in FP64. While the precise time trace of the space-averaged electrostatic heat flux $\langle Q_{es,x} \rangle$ is chaotic and clearly deviates from the reference run, the quantity of interest — its time average — is of statistical nature and turns out to be very robust.

Figure 14: **Local, single species cyclone base case. Different precisions are used to calculate the velocity space moments:** The time-averaged electrostatic heat flux is robust and reveals that here 16-bit FP types are sufficient for the moments calculation.

In addition to the quantity of interest discussed in Fig. 14, we also investigated the conservation of an invariant: In this single species run, the space-averaged electrostatic particle flux $\langle \Gamma_{es,x} \rangle$ should vanish. In Fig. 15 however, we see that numerically this holds only roughly up to the FP precision. To improve the situation, a mixed precision method is employed. In Fig. 15, in addition to the runs discussed in Fig. 14 the results for employing two improved versions (**half+**, **bfloat+**) of the moments calculation are shown: Since the moments calculation is basically a weighted summation, it is possible to considerably improve the artificial floating point error by using a higher-precision accumulator in combination with the low precision data.

Figure 15: **Electrostatic particle flux for the simulations from Fig. 14:** Although the physics imply that $\langle \Gamma_{es,x} \rangle$ vanishes, numerically this is only approximately true up to the used FP precision. A mixed precision technique for the low precision moments calculation improves the error by roughly 1.5 orders of magnitude.

Stencils: Floating point precision vs. spatial resolution

Further, we investigated the interplay of spatial resolution and FP precision in stencil computations: We consider a prototypical n -point stencil of order p to approximate the m -th spatial derivative $D^m f$ of some discrete f at position x_k of the grid, which (here for simplicity in 1D) could be written as

$$D^m f(x_k) = D^m f_k + \mathcal{O}(h^p) = \frac{\sum_{\ell=-n/2}^{n/2} c_\ell f_{k+\ell}}{h^m} + \mathcal{O}(h^p) \quad \forall k, \quad (4)$$

with the mesh size denoted by $h > 0$ and some generic stencil coefficients c_ℓ , $\ell = -n/2, \dots, n/2$.

Now, considering that the grid function f can only be represented in finite FP precision, we write $|\tilde{f} - f|_\infty < \varepsilon_{\text{FP}}$ with \tilde{f} the finite precision FP approximation to f . Plugging into (4) yields

$$|D^m f_k - D^m \tilde{f}_k| \leq \mathcal{O}(h^{-m} \varepsilon_{\text{FP}}) + \mathcal{O}(h^p) \quad \forall k. \quad (5)$$

Hence, for decreasing the mesh size $h \rightarrow 0$ the order of the finite precision stencil will degrade unless we ensure increasing the FP precision accordingly, i.e., $\varepsilon_{\text{FP}} = \mathcal{O}(h^{m+p})$ from (5). The formal computation (5) also shows that $\varepsilon_{\text{FP}} = o(h^m)$ as $h \rightarrow 0$ is required to preserve at least convergence of the finite precision stencil.

The study in Fig. 16 confirms the analytically predicted interplay of mesh resolution and FP precision for stencils: The simulation is run with three different mesh resolutions in z -direction and the corresponding stencil computation is emulated in various low precisions. For each run the error of the space-time-averaged electrostatic heat flux $Q_{es,x}$ is compared to the one obtained from a reference run in FP64 precision on the same mesh. The experiment is in clear agreement with the theoretically predicted interplay. The finer the mesh, the more FP precision is required.

In order to carry out the study in Fig. 16, we added a module for the emulation of arbitrary low precision computations to GENE. The low precision emulation is based on

Figure 16: **Local, two species nonlinear ITG run. The stencil in z -direction is emulated in different precisions:** Finer meshes require higher FP precision.

introducing random perturbations of appropriate magnitude (limited by the order of ε_{FP}) to, e.g., stencil computations. We note that it is necessary to emulate most low-precision types in software, as only a very limited set of FP precisions like FP64, FP32, FP16, or BF16 enjoy hardware support as discussed in D4.1.

Outlook

Apart from further theoretical investigations, current efforts are concerned with the implementation of a GTENSOR extension aiming to provide an elegant interface for mixed precision computations, separating data precision from compute precision and to be applicable in GENE kernels with minimal adjustments to the existing code base. Moreover, we aim to demonstrate the speedups achievable through smaller size lower precision FP types possibly in combination with mixed precision techniques [8] for various kernels within actual GENE plasma turbulence simulations. Finally, where applicable, the use of low-precision data structures can lead to reduced I/O memory requirements for checkpointing.

5 Conclusion

Compared to last year, significant improvements in parallel I/O, in-situ workflow capabilities and compression have been achieved across all codes. These improvements are timely as more codes now can leverage GPU compute power to speed up computation, thus producing more data in a shorter amount of time, which results in a significant increase in data rates. Accelerated parallel I/O, in-situ workflows and compression are all techniques to circumvent the significant reduction in bandwidth from in-memory operations to file system access and react to the relatively slow growth of storage volumes available to projects on EuroHPC systems, either by reducing simulation data during or right after production or accelerating the throughput of data analytics pipelines.

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